

Lignin-enriched cellulose membranes for efficient removal of synthetic dyes from aqueous environments

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ABSTRACT

The study presents cellulose-based membranes derived from lignin-rich (unbleached high-kappa number softwood and hardwood) and lignin-free (fully bleached softwood) kraft pulps for the removal of cationic dyes from both simulated and real aqueous environmental systems. Characterization techniques revealed that the lignin-enriched cellulose-based membranes exhibited enhanced wet mechanical properties and a broader range of functional groups. The functional diversity inherent in lignin-containing membranes resulted in superior adsorption capacity for dyes such as Methylene Blue and Crystal Violet, compared to lignin-free counterparts.

Detailed adsorption performance metrics—including kinetics, equilibrium studies, and the effects of pH and ionic strength—were thoroughly investigated. The adsorption capacity was 99–102 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ for hardwood-derived membranes and 79–85 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ for softwood-derived membranes at 25 °C. The process followed the pseudo-first-order kinetic model, likely due to the membranes' low porosity and energy homogeneity, which facilitated rapid adsorption.

Electrostatic interactions played a pivotal role in dye attraction, while pH and ionic strength studies emphasized the importance of hydrogen bonding between cationic dyes and lignocellulose-based membranes. This research highlights the significance of utilizing cellulose-based membranes with enhanced lignin content in water purification, demonstrating their effective adsorption capabilities in both controlled and real-world environments. The approbation tests of these membranes showcased their substantial potential for practical water purification applications, contributing to the development of sustainable and efficient water treatment solutions.

1. Introduction

The increasing human population and growing industrial activities have significantly impacted the environment. Environmental pollution has become one of the biggest problems in the world [1]. Huge global efforts are underway to control air, soil, and water contamination levels, to minimize risks to human health, biodiversity, and ecosystems [2].

Common hazardous contaminants such as heavy metal ions, nitrites, sulfides, antibiotics, pesticides, and N-aromatic compounds are being addressed in these efforts. Synthetic organic dyes are one of the emergent groups of water pollutants due to their large-scale production and wide applications [3]: in textile, tanning, and food processing; printing and paper industries; pharmacy, cosmetology, human and veterinary medicine. Unfortunately, around 80 % of the wastewater containing dye

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is often discharged without treatment into waterways or used directly for irrigation [4]. This irresponsible practice leads to harmful effects on both human health and ecosystems.

One effective way to reduce global pollution levels is by treating the wastewater at the source of its generation. The wastewater remediation methods are divided into three groups: chemical, biological, and physical [4]. The main advantage of physical remediation is the opportunity to extract the toxic target species without producing side metabolites. Additionally, the methods of this group allow for the recovery and reusing of pollutant species, which matches the Sustainable Global Development Goals [5]. Adsorption is one of the most efficient and economically suitable methods to remove organic dyes. Conventional resources such as zeolite [6,7], clay [8], silica composites [9,10], and carbonaceous materials [11] are widely used as adsorbents on the industrial level. Nevertheless, considering the application scale of these adsorbents, their regeneration or disposal will significantly contribute to the techno-economic perspective of the remediation process. From that point of view, low-cost adsorbents derived from biowaste residuals have gained more interest and practical attractions. For instance, technical lignin was used to remove methylene blue (MB) [12], activated carbon from Mangrove fruit [13] demonstrated high efficiency for the adsorption of MB, Malachite Green, Eriochrome Black, and Methyl Orange (MO), lignocellulose adsorbent derived from Walnut shells [14] displayed effectivity in capturing MB, methyl violet, and murexide, cellulose nanocrystals derived from microcrystalline cellulose [15] were used for selectively removing the toxic Janus Green.

Many commercial adsorbents derived from plentiful sources are available in either a powdered or granular form [16] and possess a high capacity for effective adsorption due to their suitable active sites, large surface area, and porosity. Furthermore, their surface can be easily modified to enhance their adsorption performance. However, the primary disadvantage of these adsorbents is that a large amount of them is required to achieve effective pre-treatment, which makes it more complicated to manage them during the process [16]. Membrane-based adsorbents are a new type of material that combines the benefits of both membranes and adsorbents to remove various water pollutants effectively [17]. Regenerating the membrane surface is much simpler than that of powdered or granular adsorbents, and they are also easy to manage. However, their application is limited by the surface-to-volume ratio, which can be compensated by surface hydrophilization [18]. Therefore, this type of adsorbent provides high removal efficiency while maintaining water permeability, making them an attractive option in the industry.

Various raw materials, such as chitosan, hydroxyapatite, and cellulose, are used in membrane-based adsorbents [19]. Cellulose-based membranes, in particular, offer a compelling solution for organic dye adsorption in industry wastewater treatment due to their renewable nature, biodegradability, and high efficiency [20]. These membranes exhibit excellent mechanical strength, making them robust for practical applications, while their cost-effectiveness makes them suitable for large-scale treatment processes. Furthermore, their non-toxic and biocompatible properties ensure minimal environmental impact, aligning with global sustainability goals [20]. Additionally, the ability to regenerate and reuse cellulose-based membranes multiple times provides an economically viable and sustainable option for mitigating dye pollution in industrial wastewater.

Recently, lignin-rich nanocellulose has emerged as an interesting candidate for various applications. It combines the dual advantages of better cost-effectiveness from the high-yield and low-cost raw pulp materials and the unique characteristics preserved from residual lignin [21–23]. It has been reported that residual lignin could provide the membranes with better structural integrity in aqueous environments [24]. In this study, lignin-rich microfibrillated cellulose membranes, produced from high-kappa-number unbleached kraft pulps, were investigated as novel potential adsorbent membranes for the removal of synthetic organic dyes, methylene blue (MB) and crystal violet (CV). We

hypothesize that the presence of lignin will enhance the membrane's wet tensile strength, adsorption capacity, and selectivity.

2. Experimental

2.1. Chemicals and reagents

Laboratory-prepared high kappa number softwood kraft pulp (Scandinavian pine) and hardwood kraft pulp (Eucalyptus) were provided by Valmet AB, with a kappa number of 64 and 97, respectively. The fully bleached softwood kraft pulp (Mixture of spruce and pine) was obtained from SCA. These three raw pulps were denoted as LSKP, LHKP, and BSKP, respectively. CV ($\geq 90\%$), MB ($\geq 95\%$), acids (acetic (99–100%), boric (99%), hydrochloric (37%), phosphoric (85%), sulfuric acid (72%)), salts (calcium chloride dihydrate ($>99\%$), magnesium sulfate heptahydrate ($>98\%$), potassium chloride (99%), sodium bicarbonate (99.7%), sodium carbonate (99.5%), sodium chloride (99%), sodium fluoride ($>99\%$), sodium nitrate ($>99\%$), sodium phosphate monobasic ($>99\%$)), sodium hydroxide (99%) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used without any purification. The solutions for adsorption experiments were prepared using deionized water.

2.2. Preparation of MFC and LMFC membranes

The microfibrillated cellulose (MFC) and lignin-rich microfibrillated cellulose (LMFC) membranes were prepared based on a previous study reported by Li et al. [25]. To achieve a better fiber swelling ability, LSKP, LHKP, and BSKP were first washed into Na^+ form using sodium carbonate, hydrochloric acid, and deionized water alternatively [26]. Afterward, the raw pulp fibers were refined in a laboratory PFI mill at a level of 30,000 revolutions and then mechanically fibrillated via a Supermasscolloider (Model: MKZA 10-15 J) to obtain nano/micro-sized cellulose fibers MFC and LMFC gels.

To prepare MFC and LMFC membranes, obtained MFC and LMFC gels were first diluted to a concentration of 0.2 wt% and then stirred for 10 min using Ultra Turrax at 12000 rpm. Ultra Turrax was used to high-shear disperse the MFC and LMFC suspension to achieve a uniform dispersion of cellulose fibers. Afterward, all suspensions were vacuum filtrated through a 0.65 μm DVPP membrane (Durapore) before drying in a Rapid Köthen sheet former at $93 \pm 2\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 15 min. The microfibrillated cellulose fibers prepared from fully bleached (lignin-free) softwood pulp and lignin-rich softwood and hardwood kraft pulp were denoted as MFC-SW, LMFC-SW, and LMFC-HW, correspondingly.

2.3. Characterization

Chemical composition of raw pulps. The Chemical compositions of raw pulps were determined by acid hydrolysis, including Klason lignin content and monosaccharide compositions. Specifically, around 0.2 g of the dried pulp was digested using sulfuric acid (72%) under vacuum and then diluted before being kept in an autoclave for 1 h at 121 $^\circ\text{C}$. The acid-insoluble lignin (Klason lignin) was collected by filtration and the weight was recorded. The monosaccharide compositions after hydrolysis were determined using anion-exchange chromatography Dionex ICS-3000 (HPAEC-PAD) [25].

Pyrolysis-Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry/Fire Ionization Detector (Py-GC/MS/FID). The analysis of analytical pyrolysis, Py-GC/MS/FID, was conducted according to Ponomarenko et al. [27] using a Frontier Lab (Fukushima, Japan) Micro Double-shot Pyrolyser Py-2020iD, coupled with a Shimadzu GC/MS-QP 2010 apparatus with a capillary column RTX-1701. The injector and ion source temperatures were set at 250 $^\circ\text{C}$, with EI of 70 eV. Helium was used as the carrier gas at a flow rate of 1 mL min^{-1} , with a split ratio of 1:30. Pyrolysis was performed at 500 $^\circ\text{C}$. Each sample, 1–2 mg, with residual moisture content below 1%, was analyzed. The oven program was isothermal at 60 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 min, followed by a ramp of 6 K min^{-1} to 270 $^\circ\text{C}$, and then

held at 270 °C for 10 min. The mass spectrometer operated in electron impact mode with 70 eV electron energy, and the relative error of the measurements was 1–3 %. The relative areas of the peaks of individual compounds were calculated from GC/FID data using Shimadzu software. The molar areas of the relevant peaks were summed and normalized to 100 %, and the data for three repetitive pyrolysis experiments were averaged. The content of lignin, carbohydrates, sulfur-containing compounds, and other identified compounds was calculated as the ratio of the sum of the areas of the peaks from the corresponding component divided by the sum of the area of all used peaks multiplied by 100 % [28]. The pyrolysis analysis was conducted four times, and the results were averaged. The measurement variability, expressed as the coefficient of variation, did not exceed 5 % [29].

Conductometric titration. The total charge or total carboxylate content of pulp fibers was measured by conductometric titration according to Katz et al. [30] on a Metrohm titrator (Titrino 702SM). Briefly, the pulp fibers were soaked in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ HCl to convert them to the protonated form before titration, followed by washing with deionized water until the conductivity of the filtrate was below 5 µS/cm. Subsequently, 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaOH was used as the titration agent, and the carboxylate content was determined based on the amount of NaOH consumed.

Microscopy. The Surface morphologies of MFC and LMFC membranes were observed using field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM S-4800, Hitachi). All samples were cut and then sputter coated in a 208HR Cressington Sputter Coater before SEM observation (Cressington Scientific Instruments, Watford, UK).

Specific Surface Area (SSA). Nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherm at -196 °C were recorded in the ASAP 2020 instrument (Micrometrics). The degassing was performed at 120 °C for 24 h under a dynamic vacuum. The data SSA_{BET} were calculated using the BET method and Micromeritics MicroActive software.

Mechanical Properties. The mechanical properties of all membranes were measured using an Instron 5944 tester. Firstly, all samples were cut into strips with a width of 5 mm and a length of 55 mm and then immersed in deionized water for 48 h before the mechanical test. A constant elongation rate of 5 mm min⁻¹ was used for the wet mechanical test and each measurement was repeated at least five times.

pH of the point of zero charges (pH_{pzc}). The pH drift method was used to evaluate the pH_{pzc} of the prepared membranes. The desired initial pH (pH_i) of the supporting electrolyte solution (0.01 mol L⁻¹ NaCl) was adjusted by adding 0.01 mol L⁻¹ HCl or 0.01 mol L⁻¹ NaOH. 0.01 g of lignin samples were added to 10 mL of solution and shaken for 12 h. Then, the solid was filtered off and the solution's final pH (pH_e) was measured.

FTIR Spectroscopy. Spectra were recorded in ATR mode on a Bruker Tensor 27 ATR-FTIR Spectrometer (Bruker).

2.4. Adsorption study

The adsorption performance of the prepared membranes was probed using two cationic dyes, MB and CV, through the batch technique procedures. The cut membrane pieces (5 mm vs 5 mm) were accurately weighed (2.5 mg) and placed in flasks with solutions of the desired composition (adsorbent dosage 0.5 g L⁻¹). The flasks were shaken in an Orbital Shaker INC/REFRIG 5000IR at 130 rpm and 25 °C (except the experiments for temperature effect) for 5 h (shaking time only varied in the kinetics study). Then, the residual dye concentrations were determined utilizing spectrophotometry in a UV-3100PC spectrophotometer at 664 nm (MB) and 590 nm (CV). The specific concentration of the adsorbed dye (q , µmol g⁻¹) and removal efficiency (R , %) were calculated using the following equations:

$$q = \frac{C_i - C_e}{m_s} \times V \quad (1)$$

$$R = \frac{C_i - C_e}{C_i} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

where C_i and C_e are the initial and equilibrium dye concentrations (µmol L⁻¹), respectively, m_s (g) is the weight of the membrane and V (L) is the volume of the initial solution. All experiments were repeated at least three times and the presented data were averaged. The uncertainties were between 1 and 3 %.

The pH effect was investigated in Briton-Robinson buffer (BRb, 0.02 mol L⁻¹) ranging from 5 to 7 pH. The desired pH value was adjusted by adding 1 mol L⁻¹ NaOH. The effect of ionic strength was evaluated in the presence of KCl (0.25–0.75 mol L⁻¹). The kinetics was studied in the range of 15 min – 24 h. The concentrations of dyes in those experiments were 24.5 µmol L⁻¹ (for MFC-SW) and 73.6 µmol L⁻¹ for (LMFC-SW and LMFC-HW). The isotherm study experiments were carried out in solutions containing up to 122.5 µmol L⁻¹ of dyes at 25 °C for all membranes and at 15 °C and 35 °C for LMFC-SW and LMFC-HW. No buffer was used for ionic strength, kinetic, and isotherm experiments, and the initial pH of the solutions was equal to the pH of distilled water, 6–6.5.

The practical utility of the prepared membranes was evaluated in simulated and real water samples: 1) simulated groundwater (SGW) at pH 6.5 [31]; 2) actual natural river water (ARW) at pH 7.5. The concentration of each dye was 4 µmol L⁻¹. The precisely weighted mass of dye was dissolved in the target water samples and the same water sample performed the required dilution. The absorbance of solutions was registered within 380–800 nm. The efficiency removal was evaluated based on the changes in the area under the spectra curves using the modified Eq. (2). Due to the pollution of river samples by different macro- and microelements, dissolved gases, organic matter, and admixtures, the calculation was performed assuming the water matrix components have a higher ability to be adsorbed on the membranes than dyes. For this, the changes in absorbance spectra of river water without dyes were subtracted from those where dyes were added.

2.5. Adsorption kinetics and equilibrium models

Kinetics and equilibrium data were fitted using the Microcal Origin (2019) software.

Three adsorption kinetic models [32] were applied to fit kinetic data: the pseudo-first-order (PFO) model

$$q_t = q_e \times (1 - \exp(-k_1 \bullet t)) \quad (3)$$

the pseudo-second-order (PSO) model.

$$q_t = \frac{k_2 \bullet q_e^2 \bullet t}{1 + k_2 \bullet q_e \bullet t} \quad (4)$$

the mixed 1,2-order (MOE) model.

$$q_t = q_e \times \frac{1 - \exp(-k_1 \bullet t)}{1 - f_2 \bullet \exp(-k_1 \bullet t)} \quad (5)$$

where q_t and q_e (µmol g⁻¹) are the specific concentrations of dye at time t (min) and equilibrium, k_1 (min⁻¹) and k_2 (g µmol⁻¹ min⁻¹) are PFO and PSO rate constants, f_2 is the fractional contribution of the second-order term to the entire adsorption process.

The initial sorption rates h_0 (µmol g⁻¹ min⁻¹) were estimated using the equation proposed by Ho [33]:

$$h_0 = k_n \times q_e^n \quad (6)$$

where k_n and q_e are parameters of the most applicable model, and n is the order of the kinetic model.

The Langmuir (7), Freundlich (8), and Langmuir-Freundlich (9) models [32] were used to fit the adsorption isotherms:

$$q_e = \frac{Q_{max} \cdot K_L \cdot C_e}{1 + K_L \cdot C_e} \quad (7)$$

$$q_e = K_F \times C_e^{1/n_F} \quad (8)$$

$$q_e = \frac{Q_{max} \cdot (K_{LF} \cdot C_e)^{n_{LF}}}{1 + (K_L \cdot C_e)^{n_{LF}}} \quad (9)$$

where, Q_{max} ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$) is the maximum adsorption capacity of the membranes, K_L ($\text{L } \mu\text{mol}^{-1}$), K_F ($\text{L}^{1/n_F} \mu\text{mol}^{1-1/n_F} \text{g}^{-1}$), and K_{LF} ($\text{L } \mu\text{mol}^{-1}$) are Langmuir, Freundlich and Langmuir-Freundlich equilibrium constants, n_F and n_{LF} are the dimensionless exponents of Freundlich and Langmuir-Freundlich models related to the heterogeneity of the adsorption process.

Statistical adequacy of the models was evaluated based on the adjusted determination coefficient (R_{adj}^2), standard deviation of residues (SD), and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) [34], which were calculated according to the equations:

$$R_{adj}^2 = 1 - (1 - R^2) \times \left(\frac{l - 1}{l - p - 1} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{1}{l - p} \times \sum_i^l (q_{i,model} - q_{i,exp})^2} \quad (11)$$

$$BIC = l \times \ln \left(\frac{\sum_i^l (q_{i,model} - q_{i,exp})^2}{l} \right) + p \times \ln(l) \quad (12)$$

where l and p are the numbers of experimental points and fitting parameters, correspondingly, $q_{i,model}$ and $q_{i,exp}$ are calculated and measured adsorption values (q_t for kinetic and q_e for equilibrium models). The values R_{adj}^2 closer to 1.0 and the lowest SD are attributes of the best-fitted model. The parameter BIC is used to estimate whether the difference between two models with very close R_{adj}^2 and SD is significant or whether both models provide fitting within the permissible deviations. The difference in BIC values lower than 2 means no significant difference between the models. When it lies within 2–6 the model with lower BIC shows a positive perspective for fitting. If the BIC values of the two models differ within 6–10 there is a strong possibility the model with a lower BIC value would be the best one to approximate data. Finally, if variations of BIC values are higher than 10, we can predict with accuracy the model with the lower BIC value provides better fitting.

The thermodynamic parameters were evaluated using the approach proposed by Lima et al. [35]. Despite the limitations and assumptions, the methodology is sufficient for roughly estimating the temperature effect on a qualitative level. According to it, the Van't Hoof equation is represented as:

$$\ln(K_e^\circ) = -\frac{\Delta H^\circ}{8.31 T} + \frac{\Delta S^\circ}{8.31} \quad (13)$$

where ΔH° and ΔS° are adsorption enthalpy and entropy, K_e° is the dimensionless thermodynamic equilibrium constant. The latter is calculated as

$$K_e^\circ = \frac{1000 \times K^* \times [\text{adsorbate}]^\circ}{\gamma} \quad (14)$$

where K^* is an equilibrium constant of the best isotherm model fitted, $[\text{adsorbate}]^\circ$ is the standard concentration of the adsorbate (1 mol L^{-1}), γ is the coefficient of activity. For very diluted solutions, the statement that $\gamma \rightarrow 1$ is accurate.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Material characterization

From the physical appearance of the three pulps, LSKP and LHKP showed a light-brown color due to residual lignin. The SEM images shown in Fig. 1 further depict the morphology difference of softwood and hardwood pulp fibers. Softwood pulp fibers are typically longer, thicker, and have a higher aspect ratio (length-to-width ratio), while hardwood pulp fibers are shorter and thinner than softwood fibers [21,36]. Generally, the length of softwood pulp fibers is 3–4 times greater than hardwood pulp. Similarly, the width of softwood pulp is almost twice that of its hardwood counterparts [37]. Softwood and hardwood pulp fibers also differ in their chemical composition due to the distinct characteristics of their resources. While both types of fibers consist mainly of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin, the proportions of these components vary between three different pulps. The chemical compositions of three raw pulps were analyzed using the acid hydrolysis method and the results were depicted in Fig. 1. While the bleaching process removed most of the lignin components, a shallow lignin's content was showcased with only around 1 % Klason lignin remaining in BSKP. At the same time, LSKP and LHKP preserved a high content of Klason lignin. Notably, besides the Klason lignin, the other components include hemicelluloses, and cellulose components refer to extractives, ashes, acid-soluble lignin content, and so on. Hardwood species typically present a higher acid-insoluble lignin content than softwood, especially for unbleached pulps [21,38].

After the microfibrillation steps, the three raw pulps fiber samples were broken down into nano/micro-sized cellulose fibers. When water is removed from the aqueous fiber suspensions, a robust film can form, in which the fiber networks are formed via the interfibrillar H-bonding [39]. In this study, MFC-SW and LMFC membranes were produced from lignin-free and lignin-rich softwood and hardwood microfibrillated cellulose fibers via a vacuum-assisted filtration method. The surface structures of all membranes are shown in Fig. 2, where the dense structures formed by the interconnected cellulose fibers can be observed in the SEM images.

The wet strength of membranes is a key parameter for their practical usage as filtration membranes for wastewater treatments. A higher wet strength indicates a better resistance to external stress and higher stiffness of the membranes in an aqueous environment. The wet tensile strength of MFC-SW, LMFC-SW, and LMFC-HW are shown in Fig. 3a and b and Table S2. Membranes produced from softwood resources (both MFC and LMFC-SW membranes) showed a higher wet tensile strength of 10.1 MPa and 13.3 MPa, respectively, compared to LMFC-HW with an average wet tensile strength of 8.9 MPa as displayed in Table S2, which likely benefited from the higher aspect ratio of microfibrillated cellulose fibers produced from softwood. Longer fibers could help to maintain better structure integrity with the larger number of formed fiber joints in an aqueous environment [40]. The wet strength of LMFC-SW is also higher than the reported methylene diphenyl diisocyanate-modified commercial filter paper with a wet tensile strength of 4.8 MPa after cross-linking treatments [41]. Nair et al. reported that the films prepared using lignin-containing cellulose nanofibrils with different lignin contents [24] showed similar wet strength to the membranes reported in this study.

The physicochemical properties of the prepared membranes were evaluated in the context of functional groups introduced by the membrane components. The total carboxylate content of MFC-SW, LMFC-SW, and LMFC-HW samples evaluated by conductometric titration is shown in Fig. 3c. The membrane produced from fully bleached softwood pulp contained $53.4 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ of carboxylic groups, while membranes from lignin-rich unbleached pulp had $131.5 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ (softwood) and $160 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ (hardwood) of COO^- . However, conductometric titration doesn't measure other acidic groups, phenolic hydroxyls, which make up a significant part of lignin functionality. To address the issue,

Fig. 1. Digital photos and SEM images of raw pulps a) BSKP, b) LSKP, and c) LHKP; Chemical compositions of raw pulps d) BSKP, e) LSKP, and f) LHKP.

Fig. 2. Digital photos of prepared a) MFC-SW, b) LMFC-SW, and c) LMFC-HW membranes; SEM images of d) MFC-SW, e) LMFC-SW, and f) LMFC-HW membranes.

Fig. 3. Membranes' mechanical and physicochemical properties: a) typical stress-strain curves of MFC and LMFC membranes at wet status; b) wet tensile strength of all membranes; c) total carboxylate content of produced MFC-SW, LMFC-SW, and LMFC-HW samples.

analytical technique Py-GC/MS/FID was utilized to evaluate the qualitative content of lignin fragments in membranes, and the information about the relative content of phenolic hydroxyls was derived from the obtained data. The membrane obtained from fully bleached softwood pulp (MFC-SW) showed minimal lignin content (0.71 %), primarily consisting of degraded lignin fragments, particularly phenyl and benzyl derivatives. It resulted in a limited variety of functional groups in MFC-SW, mainly composed of aliphatic hydroxyls from cellulose and hemicellulose units. The pyrolysis data for the membrane obtained from softwood unbleached pulp (LMFC-SW) showed a significant presence of guaiacyl (G) units (4.30 %), which are characterized by one methoxy group ($-\text{OCH}_3$) attached to the aromatic ring. Common pyrolysis products for softwood (guaiacyl) lignin include guaiacol, vanillin, and coniferyl alcohol. The functional groups inferred from these compounds are methoxy groups, contributing to softwood lignin's stability and lower reactivity, and hydroxyl groups, present as aliphatic and aromatic hydroxyls, contributing to the LMFC-SW's chemical properties. The hardwood membranes (LMFC-HW) were characterized by fewer G units (3.81 %) but with higher content of syringyl (S) units (14.24 %). Syringyl lignin produces pyrolysis products such as syringol, syringaldehyde, and sinapyl alcohol (see Table S1). Functional groups inferred from these compounds include a higher concentration of methoxy groups than softwood lignin, as syringyl (S) units, which are abundant in hardwood lignin, contain two methoxy groups on the aromatic ring, compared to the single methoxy group present in guaiacyl (G) units typical of softwood lignin. This leads to a less condensed structure and increased reactivity of lignin fraction in LMFC-HW. Estimating the direct correlation between lignin content and adsorption capacities is quite challenging. Table S1 presents information regarding the lignin derivative content. However, the question regarding the number of active and available functional groups remains unanswered. Given that the amounts of phenyl+benzyl and Guaiacyl derivatives are almost the same for both LMFC-SW and LMFC-HW, the latter should have a significantly greater adsorption capacity than the softwood variant. However, in reality, LMFC-SW has approximately 80 % of the capacity of LMFC-HW. The number of active adsorption centers does not increase linearly with the number of functional groups due to the effects of cooperativity, conformational changes, and the involvement of intramolecular hydrogen bonding. In addition, we have recently demonstrated that lignin functional groups have different removal efficiency, which follows the trend benzylic $-\text{OH} > -\text{COOH} > \text{AlipOH} > \text{PhOH}$. Given that LMFC-HW has a higher number of carboxylic groups, we introduce an additional variable parameter in our system for correlating adsorption capacity with functional groups.

3.2. Adsorption performance of the prepared membranes

3.2.1. Material perspectives as adsorbent

Adsorbent performance depends on two crucial factors: surface functionalities and porosity. Considering the composition of membranes, adsorption could be caused by the presence of aliphatic hydroxyls (from cellulose, hemicelluloses, and lignin fragments), phenolic hydroxyls from lignin, and carboxylic groups from both lignin and hemicelluloses. Due to the acidic nature of the latest groups [42], the membrane surfaces were expected to demonstrate an anionic character in an aqueous environment. The pH_{pzc} and the pH drift method were used as a simple and reliable technique to estimate this characteristic. The obtained pH drift of the water-membranes system vs. pH_i is shown in Fig. 4a. The estimated values of pH_{pzc} were found to be 6.1, 5.9, and 5.8 for MFC-SW, LMFC-SW and LMFC-HW, correspondingly. The resemblance in the values is attributed to the fact that cellulose and hemicellulose are the main components of these membranes, contributing from 90 % to 61 %. As shown in Fig. 3c, lignin-rich samples exhibited a higher carboxylate content compared to lignin-free counterparts, this contributes to their lower pH_{pzc} values. To summarize, all three materials bear a negative surface net charge during contact with a

Fig. 4. (a) pH_{pzc} of membranes; (b) structural formulas of MB⁺ (top) and CV⁺ (bottom); (c) adsorption isotherms of MB⁺ (top) and CV⁺ (bottom) (symbols) and non-linear fitting by the equilibrium models (lines); (d) influence of contact time on MB⁺ (top) and CV⁺ (bottom) adsorption (symbols) and non-linear fitting by the kinetic models (lines). Note: the symbol size in figures a, c, and d is equivalent to the average uncertainty of measurement (2 %).

typical aqueous environment (pH 6.5–7.5). This makes attractive adsorption of cationic species by the adsorbent manufactured from these membranes.

Porosity is another crucial factor in the material's ability to remove contaminants by providing spaces where pollutants can be trapped. The nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms were registered at -196°C to evaluate whether materials are porous. The results indicated very low SSA_{BET} values: MFC-SW = $5 \pm 2 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, LMFC-SW = $3.1 \pm 0.4 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and LMFC-HW = $11.7 \pm 0.6 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$. These low values suggest that the

materials are not inherently porous. Consequently, the primary mechanism for the adsorption is likely the functional groups of the materials rather than porosity.

3.2.2. Adsorption capacities

The adsorption capacity is one of the main characteristics concerning materials applicable as adsorbents at the industrial scale. Considering the anionic nature of the membrane surface, the adsorption performance of the prepared MFC-SW, LMFC-SW, and LMFC-HW was elucidated

using two cationic dyes, MB⁺ and CV⁺ (Fig. 4b). The obtained equilibrium isotherms and the fitting curves of Langmuir, Freundlich, and Langmuir-Freundlich models are presented in Fig. 4c, and the models' parameters were collected in Table 1. Considering the *SD* and R_{adj}^2 statistical criteria, the Freundlich model provided worse approximations of experimental data since it showed the highest *SD* and lowest R_{adj}^2 values for all studied adsorption systems. In the case of MFC-SW, both Langmuir and Langmuir-Freundlich models displayed resembled values of statistical criteria. The nearness of parameter n_{LF} (0.95 for CV⁺ and 0.9 for MB⁺) to unity and the difference of *BIC* parameters (less two unities) indicate no significant difference between the models, and the adsorption mechanism follows ideal monolayer adsorption for both dyes. The homogeneous character of the MFC-SW surface could be explained by membrane composition (cellulose contributes more than 75 %) and low concentration of adsorption centers, which are evenly distributed. Considering the adsorption of dyes onto lignin-rich films LMFC-SW and LMFC-HW, Langmuir-Freundlich showed more perspectives to fit experimental data: the lower *SD* and *BIC* parameters (especially in the case of LMFC-HW), higher R_{adj}^2 values. The values of parameter n_{LF} were 0.78 (CV⁺) and 0.52 (MB⁺) for LMFC-SW, and 0.63 (for both dyes) for LMFC-HW, indicating the adsorbent active sites have different energy and adsorption process poses heterogeneous character. In contrast to MFC-SW, lignin-rich membranes have more diverse compositions, resulting in the coexistence of functional groups with different affinity to the adsorbed dyes, reflecting surface heterogeneity.

The maximum adsorption capacities were observed for membrane

Table 1

The results of fitting equilibrium adsorption isotherm of CV and MB onto the prepared membranes.

	MFC-SW		LMFC-SW		LMFC-HW	
	CV	MB	CV	MB	CV	MB
$Q_{max,exp}$ $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ (mg g^{-1})	12 ± 1 (4.7 ± 0.4)	17 ± 2 (4.8 ± 0.6)	85 ± 3 (32 ± 1)	79 ± 4 (22 ± 1)	99 ± 3 (37 ± 1)	102 ± 4 (29 ± 1)
Langmuir model						
$Q_{max,cab}$ $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$	13.2 ± 0.3	19.9 ± 0.9	83 ± 3	74 ± 3	95 ± 4	99 ± 3
K_L , L μmol^{-1}	0.18 ± 0.02	0.17 ± 0.02	0.9 ± 0.2	1.5 ± 0.5	1.0 ± 0.2	0.9 ± 0.1
R_{adj}^2	0.9883	0.9779	0.9651	0.9382	0.9603	0.9755
<i>SD</i> , $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$	0.37	0.75	5.96	6.91	6.96	5.69
<i>BIC</i>	-17.6	-2.9	42.7	45.1	45.3	40.9
Freundlich model						
K_F , L ^{1/n_F} $\mu\text{mol}^{1-1/n_F}$ g^{-1}	3.5 ± 0.5	4.8 ± 0.5	36 ± 5	38 ± 3	41 ± 5	45 ± 4
n_F	0.34 ± 0.04	0.38 ± 0.04	0.22 ± 0.03	0.19 ± 0.02	0.22 ± 0.03	0.22 ± 0.02
R_{adj}^2	0.9192	0.9488	0.8430	0.9169	0.8653	0.9287
<i>SD</i> , $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$	0.97	1.1	12.0	8.0	13.5	9.72
<i>BIC</i>	1.7	4.6	57.3	48.4	59.9	52.6
Langmuir-Freundlich model						
$Q_{max,cab}$ $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$	12.8 ± 0.9	22 ± 2	87 ± 3	87 ± 4	105 ± 2	112 ± 2
K_{LF} , L μmol^{-1}	0.19 ± 0.03	0.14 ± 0.06	0.75 ± 0.09	0.9 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.1	0.61 ± 0.04
n_{LF}	0.95 ± 0.09	0.85 ± 0.09	0.78 ± 0.05	0.52 ± 0.05	0.63 ± 0.03	0.63 ± 0.02
R_{adj}^2	0.9890	0.9764	0.9733	0.9905	0.9886	0.9991
<i>SD</i> , $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$	0.36	0.8	5.02	2.71	3.17	1.07
<i>BIC</i>	-15.9	-1.5	39.4	25.6	27.6	5.2

LMFC-HW (99 ± 3 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ for CV⁺ and 102 ± 4 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ for MB⁺), with removal efficiency of 40.8 % and 42.1 %, correspondingly. In comparison, the membrane MFC-SW demonstrated the lowest capacities (12 ± 1 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ for CV⁺ and 17 ± 2 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ for MB⁺) with efficiency of 12.3 % and 20.6 %, respectively. In contrast to these two membranes, LMFC-SW demonstrated a slightly higher affinity to CV than MB, however, capacities differed within uncertainties: 85 ± 3 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ for CV⁺ and 79 ± 4 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ for MB⁺ at the removal efficiency of 34.4 % and 32.0 %, correspondingly. Summarizing, the lignin-rich membranes show perspective to be used as adsorbents for removing cationic organic species regardless of the planar or bulkier structures of organic contaminants compared to lignin-free counterparts.

3.2.3. Kinetics

The adsorption rate is another crucial parameter regarding the practical applicability of the adsorbent system on a large scale. The influence of contact time on the adsorption was investigated for dye concentrations representing the high-concentration region in the equilibrium studies. Fig. 4d shows the experimental data and the fitting plots obtained using PFO, PSO, and MOE kinetic models, while its parameters are collected in Table 2. Comparing the statistical criteria *SD* and R_{adj}^2 showed that PFO fitted the experimental data better than PSO in all studied cases. The differences between *BIC* parameters in the couple PFO/PSO were higher by eight and more in favor of PFO, indicating this model is the best one to approximate experimental data. Considering the results of MOE, two parameters k_1 and f_2 , have to be noted. The obtained values of k_1 demonstrated a resemblance to the counterparts of the PFO model. The parameters f_2 deviated within the range of 0–0.3 with significant uncertainties (for MFC-SW optimal parameters had even negative values), indicating the fractional contribution of the PSO term is limiting to negligibility in the total adsorption process. This observation is in good agreement with the analysis of the statistical criteria. The unusual applicability of PFO is explained by the relatively low porosity of membranes and energy homogeneity due to the domination of cellulose in membrane compositions. Noteworthy lignin-containing membranes LMFC-SW and LMFC-HW demonstrated a decrease in homogeneity since the parameters f_2 have factual values, indicating the insignificant contribution of PSO. This agrees with the equilibrium studies showing that the Langmuir-Freundlich model better fits experimental data than the Langmuir model.

The calculated values of initial adsorption rates are presented in Table 2. The obtained values varied within 2–3.3 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$ except for CV adsorption onto MFC-SW, where the initial rate was 0.23. All three membranes demonstrated higher rates of MB adsorption than CV. This phenomenon is explained by greater mobility and faster diffusion of MB due to a more linear structure, smaller molecular size, and weight in contrast to the trigonal planar and bulkier structure of CV [43]. In the case of MB adsorption, 50 % removal was achieved in less than 9 min (MFC-SW), 15 min (LMFC-SW), and 22 min (LMFC-HW). In contrast, the same CV removal was obtained for 31 min, 25 min, and 30 min, respectively. 90 % removal efficiencies of MB and CV were reached for 16 and 117 min (MFC-SW), 72 and 90 min (LMFC-SW), and 72 and 120 min (LMFC-HW). Considering the studied dyes' concentrations correspond to the plateau in equilibrium isotherms, both lignin-containing membranes demonstrate fast kinetics, which makes these materials attractive for practical applications.

3.2.4. Effect of pH, ionic strength and temperature on adsorption performance

pH of the solution is an important factor in the adsorption process since it influences both the adsorbent surface and adsorbate species. Water resources have different pH values depending on their origin. For example, natural water resources (streams, rivers, lakes) have a pH of 6.0–8.5 depending on the surrounding environment, while greenhouse water [44] is within the range of 5.4–6.8. Considering that CV is a

Table 2

The results of kinetics adsorption fitting of CV and MB onto the prepared membranes with dyes concentration $24.5 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ (for MFC-SW) and $73.6 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ for (LMFC-SW and LMFC-HW).

	MFC-SW		LMFC-SW		LMFC-HW	
	CV	MB	CV	MB	CV	MB
$q_{e,exp}$, $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ (mg g^{-1})	10.0 ± 0.5 (3.7 ± 0.2)	15.3 ± 0.4 (4.3 ± 0.1)	85.0 ± 0.8 (31.6 ± 0.3)	76.7 ± 0.6 (21.8 ± 0.2)	93.1 ± 0.8 (34.9 ± 0.3)	96.6 ± 0.6 (27.4 ± 0.2)
Pseudo-first-order model						
$q_{e,calc}$, $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$	10.0 ± 0.1	15.3 ± 0.1	83.3 ± 0.9	75.8 ± 0.9	92.6 ± 0.8	97 ± 1
k_1 , min^{-1}	0.023 ± 0.001	0.134 ± 0.002	0.030 ± 0.001	0.039 ± 0.003	0.022 ± 0.001	0.033 ± 0.002
R^2_{adj}	0.9836	0.9840	0.9848	0.9755	0.9945	0.9759
SD , $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$	0.30	0.079	2.21	2.18	1.70	2.97
BIC	-23.9	-53.2	20.0	20.0	14.2	26.6
Pseudo-second-order model						
$q_{e,calc}$, $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$	10.9 ± 0.3	15.6 ± 0.1	90 ± 2	81 ± 2	101 ± 3	104 ± 3
k_2 , $\text{g } \mu\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$	0.003 ± 0.002	0.033 ± 0.009	$5 \cdot 10^{-4} \pm 2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$8 \cdot 10^{-4} \pm 1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-4} \pm 1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-4} \pm 2 \cdot 10^{-4}$
R^2_{adj}	0.9573	0.6983	0.9446	0.9363	0.9581	0.9118
SD , $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$	0.48	0.34	4.21	3.16	4.68	5.69
BIC	-13.4	-20.8	34.2	27.9	36.6	40.8
Mixed 1,2-order rate equation model						
$q_{e,calc}$, $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$	10.1 ± 0.1	15.3 ± 0.2	84 ± 1	77 ± 1	92.8 ± 0.9	97 ± 1
k_1 , min^{-1}	0.017 ± 0.004	0.29 ± 0.03	0.027 ± 0.006	0.020 ± 0.008	0.020 ± 0.003	0.031 ± 0.008
f_2	-1 ± 2	-10 ± 5	0.1 ± 0.3	0.3 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.3
R^2_{adj}	0.9856	0.9995	0.9833	0.9615	0.9941	0.9733
SD , $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$	0.28	0.013	2.31	2.45	1.77	3.13
BIC	-24.22	-90.2	22.1	23.5	16.2	28.8
h_0 , $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$	0.23 ± 0.02	2.06 ± 0.05	2.51 ± 0.03	2.98 ± 0.03	2.08 ± 0.04	3.23 ± 0.05

triarylmethane dye, which becomes colorless [45] upon reaction with hydroxyl ions due to π -conjugation, the pH effect on the dyes' adsorption was evaluated within the range of 5–7. The obtained results were collected in Figs. 5a and 5b.

In general, utilizing the buffer led to a negative effect – the removal efficiency values dropped by 4–100 % depending on membrane material and pH. The MFC-SW membrane was the most sensitive to buffer components (organic and inorganic ions). Placing the membrane in the buffer reduced values of R from 31.8 % to 9.34 % at pH 7 (for MB^+) and from 20.3 % to 7.12 % at pH 7 (for CV^+). When pH shifted to 5, no adsorption of both dyes on the membrane was observed. In contrast, the adsorption performance of lignin-rich membranes was less dependent on buffer components. The LMFC-SW demonstrated relative stability at neutral pH and in distilled water, and LMFC-HW showed drops of 14.2 % (CV^+) and 22 % (MB^+). Further acidification of the adsorption system led to an insignificant cutting of removal efficiency, from 49.8 % to 34.2 % (for MB^+) and 49.3 % to 34.9 % (for CV^+) in the case of LMFC-SW, from 44.3 % to 31.2 % (for MB^+) and 49.1 % to 39.6 % (for CV^+) in the case of LMFC-HW. Based on the data, LMFC-SW and LMFC-HW are expected to perform better in real systems with organic and inorganic contaminants than lignin-free membranes. Summarizing the optimal conditions of membranes' applicability meets the typical pH range of natural water resources, making these materials attractive for water purification applications.

Water resources can contain a lot of dissolved inorganic species interfering with the adsorption behavior of the studied membranes. To elucidate their contribution, adsorption experiments were performed in the model solutions with different ionic strengths, which were created using potassium chloride. The obtained results are presented in Figs. 5c and 5d. As in the pH study, MFC-SW was the most sensitive to the presence of KCl ions, and the removal efficiency of dyes was reduced to almost zero (0.5–2.9 %) in contrast to 31.2 % (MB^+) and 20.3 % (CV^+) in the distilled water medium. Considering the low concentration of dyes, this membrane is unsuitable for practical use. Although the presence of KCl led to a decrease in the R values of lignin-rich membranes during experiments with MB^+ adsorption, the R values remained within the

range of uncertainties when salt concentration varied from 0.25 to 0.75 mol L^{-1} . This indicates that the performance of the membranes is not affected by the presence of inorganic components. In the case of CV^+ , the R values decreased by approximately 21 % for 0.25 mol L^{-1} of KCl compared with distilled water media but grew and exceeded them when electrolyte concentrations were 0.5 mol L^{-1} and higher. Overall, both lignin-rich membranes effectively remove dyes in the presence of inorganic species and have the potential for practical application.

The temperature effect on adsorption was evaluated for membranes with the highest perspectives, LMFC-SW and LMFC-HW (results presented in Figure S1 and Table S3). The equilibrium constants of the Langmuir-Freundlich model were substituted in Eq. (14) and Eq. (13), the obtained thermodynamic functions are collected in Table S3. The decrease in temperature enhances the dye adsorption. The small variations of the equilibrium constants within the studied temperature range complicate accurately estimating the thermodynamic parameters. Additionally, the fitting provides equilibrium constants, which poorly represent the Henry region [46] where the assumption regarding the coefficient of activity works. However, rough estimations indicate the adsorption process is a physical rather than a chemical phenomenon [47]. When comparing the enthalpy altitudes of different systems, the LMFC-HW/ MB system shows a higher value of change of enthalpy. This observation aligns with studies on ionic strength and pH, which indicate that the removal efficiency significantly decreases when a supporting electrolyte or a slightly acidic environment is present. Meanwhile, the other three systems show relatively slower changes in R . The reason for this could be a higher electrostatic contribution to total adsorption since electrostatic interactions have specific enthalpy [48].

3.2.5. FTIR spectra of the membranes before and after adsorption

FTIR spectroscopy was applied to elucidate the functional groups involved in the interactions with dyes. Considering the membranes' spectra (Fig. 5e) before and after dye adsorption, the resemblance in profiles indicates the existence of physical interactions rather than a chemical transformation of membrane functional groups during the adsorption process. In the case of MFC-SW, the typical bands of dye

Fig. 5. (a) and (b) the influence of pH on the adsorption of MB⁺ and CV⁺, correspondingly. (c) and (d) the influence of ionic strength on the adsorption of MB⁺ and CV⁺, correspondingly. (e) FTIR spectra of MFC-SW, LMFC-SW, and LMFC-HW before and after the adsorption of dyes. Note: distilled water (DW) – adsorption experiment performed with no additional components except dye in solution; dyes' concentrations were 24.5 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ (for MFC-SW) and 73.6 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ for (LMFC-SW and LMFC-HW).

molecules are almost invisible on the spectra due to the low adsorption capacity of the membrane. The band between 3600 and 3100 cm^{-1} , which is responsible for the stretching O–H bond in hydroxyl groups of alcohols, phenols, carboxylic acids, and absorbed water [49], showed slightly reduced intensity after adsorption. The wide and very weak band between 1700 and 1600 cm^{-1} , assigned as C=O stretch in conjugated aldehydes and carboxylic acids [50], demonstrated smoothing after dye adsorption. These changes could be due to the involvement of

the surrounding carboxylic groups in interactions with dye molecules [51], which are likely to interact with cationic dyes via an electrostatic mechanism. A slightly reduced intensity was observed at 1105 and 1030 cm^{-1} , associated with stretching C–O in secondary and primary alcohols, according to [49]. The Oxygen atom from the C–O alcohols group could act as an electron donor interacting with aromatic rings of dyes (electron acceptors) [52]. A contrast situation was observed for lignin-rich membranes with adsorbed dyes. The spectra displayed distinct

bands of dyes at 1597 cm^{-1} and 1585 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the aromatic skeletal C—C/C—N bonds in MB and CV molecules, respectively. The increased intensity of the O—H band can be linked to H-bonding between hydroxyl groups of lignin and N atoms of dyes [53], and the asymmetry of the peaks and their slight shift towards higher wavenumbers are due to the appearance of dissociated phenolate —O^- groups caused by the electrostatic interactions between the hydroxyl groups and dye cations [51]. The region between 1390 and 1360 cm^{-1} of the spectra (highlighted with green background) before adsorption have a band at 1370 cm^{-1} due to O—H bending in phenolic fragments [50]. This peak nearly vanishes in the spectra when MB was adsorbed, indicating electrostatic interactions, as recently demonstrated [51]. Unfortunately, CV has a characteristic band [54] of high intensity at 1360 cm^{-1} , which makes it impossible to establish the disappearance of the O—H bending peak.

3.2.6. Possible adsorption mechanisms

When combining FTIR data with pH and ionic strength studies, it becomes evident that electrostatic interactions play a significant role in dye adsorption across all three membranes. However, their contribution differs between membranes prepared from fully bleached (lignin-free) softwood pulp and lignin-rich counterparts. Analyzing the influence of pH on adsorption performance reveals that the removal efficiency improves as the pH shifts from acidic to neutral. These observations are consistent with the pH_{pzc} study, highlighting the importance of electrostatic interactions between the negatively charged membrane surfaces and cationic dyes.

For the MFC-SW membrane, electrostatic interactions are likely the primary adsorption forces. When the pH of the adsorption system shifted from neutral (7) to slightly acidic (6), the removal efficiency (R) decreased from 9.34 % to 2.37 % for MB^+ and from 7.12 % to 1.49 % for CV^+ . However, when the pH was further reduced to 5, there was almost no adsorption of either dye on the membrane. These results suggest that while electrostatic interactions contribute to dye capture, their effect is minimal due to the low quantity of ionized species in the MFC-SW membrane. Based on the concentration of —COOH groups in MFC-SW membranes (Fig. 3c), the surface ionization is primarily caused by carboxylic groups, which act as the sole adsorption centers for attracting cationic dyes. The strict dependence of adsorption on the presence of organic and inorganic species in the system (as seen in the ionic strength study) further supports the assumption that electrostatic interactions are the primary forces involved [9]. The involvement of carboxylic groups is also consistent with FTIR data, particularly changes between 1700 and 1600 cm^{-1} in Fig. 5e). A contrasting situation is observed with the LMFC-SW and LMFC-HW membranes. Despite higher dye concentrations in the adsorption systems during the pH and ionic strength studies, the removal efficiency from acidic solution remained high for the lignin-rich membranes compared to MFC-SW. The higher number of negatively charged surface groups (membranes have lower pH_{pzc} values) and the potential binding of nitrogen-containing dyes via H-bond [51] with lignin's aliphatic hydroxyls may explain the phenomenon. The importance of electrostatic interactions in dye binding is evident from Figs. 5a and 5b, where acidification of the adsorption system reduced the removal efficiency. Electrostatic interactions with cationic dyes can occur through COOH and acidic phenolic groups [51]. However, these are not the only forces responsible for dye adsorption on the membranes' surface. As shown in Figs. 5a and 5b, a significant portion of the dyes was adsorbed even when the membranes' surfaces were positively charged. This observation, along with the FTIR data, suggests that H-bonding also contributes to dyes adsorption. When comparing the effect of KCl on the performance of lignin-rich membranes, it's important to note that the electrostatic interactions with hardwood lignin are stronger than with softwood lignin. This is because hardwood lignin contains a higher concentration of COOH (as shown in Fig. 3c) and acidic phenol derivatives (see Table S1).

3.2.7. Adsorption of dyes from simulated and actual natural water samples

To prove the practical applicability of membranes as adsorbents, all three were subjected to the treatment of a simulated groundwater sample (SGW) and an actual water sample from river (ARW). The comparison of absorption spectra of water samples with dyes before and after treatment with membranes is presented in Fig. 6.

According to the results, the membrane LMFC-SW exhibited the best water purification performance with 83.0 % (for SGW) and 77.6 % (for ARW) removal efficiency. In contrast, LMFC-HW showed slightly lower values – 73.5 % and 77.3, respectively. The membrane MFC-SW displayed the worst applicability for water treatment with R of 7.4 % (SGW) and 43.9 %. Notably, the lower removal from SGW is caused by the strong negative effect of electrolyte presence on the behavior of the MFC-SW membrane, as demonstrated in Figs. 5a and 5b. Considering the presented data, membranes rich in lignin showed promise for treating water sources abundant in organic-inorganic contaminants.

Additionally, we conducted a comparative analysis of similar membrane-adsorbents performance to assess the effectiveness of the prepared membranes for capturing organic dyes from an aqueous environment (Table S4).

4. Conclusions

This study investigated microfibrillated cellulose-based membranes derived from lignin-rich softwood and hardwood kraft pulps, as well as lignin-free fully bleached softwood pulps, as potential adsorbents for removing cationic organic dyes, specifically Methylene Blue (MB) and Crystal Violet (CV). The results demonstrated that the presence of lignin as a component of the membrane enhanced its mechanical properties and added useful functionalities for adsorption. This significantly improved its dye adsorption capacity in both single and binary-component systems, whether simulated or real.

A detailed investigation of membranes' physicochemical properties and adsorption performance revealed that electrostatic interactions are essential for dye attraction to the surface. However, the functional groups introduced by lignin, primarily hydroxyls, facilitate H-bonding with cationic dyes, thereby providing significantly higher adsorption capacities compared to lignin-free membranes. The LMFC-HW membrane, with a higher relative lignin content, exhibited an adsorption capacity of $99\text{--}102\text{ }\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$, while the LMFC-SW membrane showed an adsorption capacity of $79\text{--}85\text{ }\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$.

Additionally, studies on the effects of pH and ionic strength revealed that the performance of hardwood membranes exhibited a stronger dependency on electrostatic interactions than their softwood counterparts, due to a larger proportion of ionized groups in the membrane composition. Notably, both lignin-rich membranes demonstrated similar behavior in simulated groundwater and actual river samples.

Furthermore, producing high-lignin content unbleached kraft pulp is more environmentally friendly, resulting in higher pulp yield and lower production costs. Membrane-based adsorbents derived from this cost-effective raw material present a practical, economical, and scalable solution for water treatment, which aligns with the environmental and commercial considerations of modern industries.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Oleg Tkachenko: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Huisi Li:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Galina Dobelev:** Investigation. **Olena Sevastyanova:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Tetyana M. Budnyak:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Fig. 6. a) the water sample containing $8 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of dyes MB^+ and CV^+ in molar ratio 1:1 (middle), SGW (left), and ARW (right) after treatment with LMFC-SW; b) absorption spectra of SGW with $8 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of dyes before and after treatment with membranes; c) absorption spectra of ARW with $8 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of dyes before and after treatment with membranes.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used Grammarly/ Grammarly, Inc. and ChatGPT/OpenAI as English grammar editing tools. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.reactfunctpolym.2025.106275>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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